

Polycaprolactone/Gelatin and Polycaprolactone/MXene/Gelatin Composite Films for Biomedical Applications

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Abstract

Herein, we report the fabrication of composite films based on polycaprolactone (PCL), MXene, and gelatin prepared by solution casting intended for use e.g. as scaffold materials for biomedical engineering. Three different concentrations of gelatin derived from bovine, fish, and porcine skin were used to prepare the composites. The films were characterized for their chemical structure, morphology, physicochemical properties, cytotoxicity, biocompatibility, and cell growth. All the films exhibited high tensile strength ranging from 8.6 to 10.2 MPa. SAXS showed that the nm-scale lamellar stack structure typical for PCL was present in all samples and larger particles (> 20 nm) were observed in all composite films. On the other hand, WAXS showed that the ratio of the individual PCL reflections varied with the sample composition indicating a preferential orientation of PCL crystallites, especially in MXene-containing samples. The SEM/SE micrographs displayed a rough morphology of gelatin nanoparticles in PCL matrix and the roughness of structure decreased in the following order: PCL/MX/fish gelatin $>$ PCL/MX/bovine gelatin $>$ PCL/MX/porcine gelatin. *In vitro* cell culture experiments with SAOS-2 cells revealed that the composition of the studied films influenced cell adhesion and proliferation. The best cell growth was observed for samples with porcine gelatin in combination with MXene.

Keywords: Polycaprolactone, gelatin, MXene, nanoscale morphology, mechanical properties, biocompatibility, cytotoxicity

1. Introduction

The design of biomaterial platforms (hydrogels, films, or meshes) for tissue engineering is challenging. The biocompatibility and bioactivity of the material can influence many functions of the cells, including anchorage [1], signaling [2] and morphogenesis [3]. Biomaterials also provide physical support for tissues [4], which is crucial for all these processes. Recently, natural polysaccharides such as chitosan [5-7], alginate [8], cellulose [9, 10], hyaluronic acid [7, 11], starch [12, 13] and xanthan gum [14]); natural proteins such as gelatin [15, 16], collagen [5] and silk [8], and resorbable synthetic polymers such as polycaprolactone (PCL) [12] and poly(lactide-*co*-glycolide) (PLGA) [17, 18] have been extensively used to design these biomaterial platforms. Although natural polymers have excellent bioactivity, they produce films with insufficient mechanical properties. On the other hand, synthetic biodegradable polymers, such as PCL, PLGA and polylactide (PLA) possess good malleability and mechanical properties but lack the required bioactivity and long-term stability, which limits their direct use [19-21]. Blending natural and synthetic biodegradable polymers gives us the advantages of both types of polymers, improves the cell-polymer interaction, and allows us to control the mechanical properties and degradation rate, which are crucial factors for designing these composite films. Moreover, the incorporation of nanoparticles (NPs) can further improve the mechanical strength of these films. Studies have shown that composites developed by combining natural and synthetic polymers have shown positive results for wound healing and tissue engineering [22-24].

PCL is considered an ideal biodegradable polymer for tissue engineering applications due to its biocompatibility, structural stability, and mechanical properties [25]. PCL is an FDA-approved polymer [26] that has been shown to enhance the osteogenic potency of human mesenchymal stem cells [27], and the differentiation potency and growth of chondrocytes, fibroblasts, skeletal muscle cells, endothelial cells, and human mesenchymal stem cells [28].

Among natural polymers, gelatin is a biodegradable polymer composed of arginine-glycine-aspartic acid (RGD) sequence which mediates cell adhesion, cell proliferation, and tissue regeneration [29]. However, gelatin has low mechanical strength and a rapid degradation rate which limits its direct use. It is usually blended with other polymers or loaded with inorganic nanoparticles to improve its mechanical properties [30, 31]. Recently, the integration of MXene nanoparticles into various matrices have been shown to enhance tissue reconstruction due to the large surface area and adjustable physicochemical properties of these nanoparticles [32, 33]. MXenes are 2D materials consisting of carbides and nitrides with uneven distribution of functional groups having the formula $M_{n+1}X_nT_x$ where M refers to the transition metal, X - carbon/nitrogen, T - functional groups such as oxygen, hydroxyl, fluorine, and n is an integer [34]. Studies have also shown that the mechanical properties of materials, e.g. hydrogels, can be significantly improved by incorporating MXenes [35, 36]. Recently, double-network conductive hydrogels were prepared from silk protein, polyacrylamide and MXenes, which exhibited a high stretchability of ~4960 % [37]. In another study, He *et al.* developed MXene/Gellan gum hydrogel with strong photothermal properties for controlled anticancer drug release [38].

In the present work, we report the synthesis of biocompatible films based on PCL, MXene and gelatin for tissue engineering applications. We investigated the influence of fish, bovine and porcine gelatin on the structural, physical, and chemical properties of hydrogels using various analytical techniques: Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), light microscopy (LM), small- and wide-angle X-ray scattering (SWAXS), and dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA). *In vitro* studies were performed in order to test the biocompatibility in terms of cell adhesion and growth on the newly-developed hydrogels. A comparative analysis of the composite films with respect to their morphology, mechanical properties and cell growth was also carried out.

2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

PCL (MW = 50,000) was purchased from Polysciences, Inc. (Germany). Gelatin (Gel) from bovine skin, cold water fish skin, and porcine skin was purchased from Sigma Aldrich Co, Ltd, USA. MXene (MX; formula: Ti_2C) was obtained from Laizhou Kai Kai Ceramic Materials Co., Ltd. China. Chloroform was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich Co. Ltd, USA. All the chemicals were analytical grade and used as received.

2.2 Preparation of PCL/Gel and PCL/MX/Gel films

PCL/Gel films (PCL/B1-B3, PCL/F1-F3 and PCL/P1-P3) were prepared using one-pot synthesis by dissolving gelatin (1.2 g) in 20 ml of acetic acid and formic acid mixture (6.1) and stirring at 60 °C for 20 min. PCL (9 g) was dissolved separately in 20 ml of chloroform and stirred at 40 °C for 10 min until a homogenous solution was formed. Subsequently, PCL/Gel films were fabricated by mixing both solutions in different ratios, stirring for 10 min, and solution casting using a TQC automatic casting machine (TQC, Germany). The obtained films were dried at room temperature for 24 h, and the final thickness of the films was around 300 μ m.

PCL/MX/Gel films (PCL/MX/B1-3, PCL/MX/F1-3, and PCL/MX/P1-3) were prepared using a similar procedure as described above. Briefly, gelatin (1.2 g) was dissolved in 20 ml of acetic acid-formic acid mixture (6.1) and stirred for 20 min. PCL (9 g) was dissolved separately in chloroform (20 ml) and MXene (0.06 g) was added to the PCL solution and stirred for 10 min until a homogeneous solution was obtained. The two mixtures of PCL/MXene and gelatin solutions were then mixed, stirred for 10 min, and the films were fabricated by solution casting and dried in the same way as the PCL/Gel films. The compositions of the composite hydrogels and their respective sample codes are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Composition of PCL/Gel and PCL/MX/Gel films

<i>Sample Code</i>	<i>Dry Composition^{b)} (wt %)</i>		
	<i>PCL</i>	<i>Gelatin</i>	<i>MXene</i>
PCL	100		
PCL/B1	88	12	
PCL/B2	85	15	
PCL/B3	75	24.5	
PCL/MX/B1	88	11.5	0.5
PCL/MX/B2	84	15.5	0.5
PCL/MX/B3	75	24.5	0.5

*PCL/F1-3, PCL/P1-3 have an analogous composition to PCL/B1-3

PCL/MX/F1-3 and PCL/MX/P1-3 have an analogous composition to PCL/MX/B1-3

2.1 Physico-chemical characterization

The *infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR)* was used to analyze the chemical structure of the composite films. Infrared absorbance spectra were performed on a Nicolet 380 FTIR spectrometer in the range from 650 to 4000 cm^{-1} using the ATR (attenuated total reflection) accessory with a Ge crystal.

The *small- and wide-angle X-ray scattering (SWAXS)* experiments were carried out on a SAXSess mc^2 instrument (Anton Paar, Austria) which is a Kratky-type instrument equipped with a microfocus X-ray source with a Cu anode, single-bounce focusing X-ray optics and a collimation block. Rectangular imaging plates were used for X-ray detection. The range of the scattering vector magnitude, q , was $0.2 \text{ nm}^{-1} - 28 \text{ nm}^{-1}$; here $q = 4\pi/\lambda \sin(\theta)$, λ is the wavelength and θ is $\frac{1}{2}$ of the scattering angle. The X-ray wavelength, λ , was 0.1542 nm (CuK α line). The partly 2D (i.e., a rectangular sector) scattering patterns of the film samples

were measured in the standard, i.e., transmission mode in vacuum, perpendicular to the film surface. The 1D radial intensity profiles were calculated from the measured 2D patterns by azimuthal averaging using the software supplied with the instrument. This procedure could be performed due to the azimuthal symmetry of the scattering/diffraction patterns (thanks to the isotropic nature of the samples in the plane of the films). Then, the SWAXS profiles were separated into SAXS and WAXS profiles. The *Irena* software tool box [1] for small-angle scattering analysis was used to further process both the SAXS profiles and the WAXS profiles.

The *scanning electron microscopy* (SEM) with energy-dispersive analysis of X-rays (SEM/EDX) of top, bottom and fracture surfaces were performed with a high-resolution SEM microscope (MAIA3; Tescan; Czech Republic) equipped with an EDX detector (X-Max^N 20; Oxford Instruments, UK). Each sample was observed at the top surface (mat and rougher), bottom surface (shiny and smoother), and at the fracture surface (fracturing in liquid nitrogen, as described elsewhere [39]). The fracture surfaces were perpendicular to the top surface. Before observation, the samples were fixed with a double adhesive carbon tape to aluminum sample holders and covered with a thin platinum layer (~ 4 nm) using a vacuum sputter coater (SCD 050, Leica; Austria) to minimize possible e-beam induced charging and sample damage. The surfaces were visualized with a secondary electron detector (SEM/SE) at the accelerating voltage of 30 kV, backscattered electron detector (SEM/BSE) at 30 kV, and the elemental microanalysis from selected typical regions (SEM/EDX) was performed at 30 kV.

The *transmission electron microscopy* (TEM) was made with a TEM microscope (Tecnai G2 Spirit; FEI, Czech Republic). The ultrathin sections for TEM observations were prepared by ultramicrotomy at cryogenic conditions (ultramicrotome: Ultracut UCT, Leica, Austria; sample and knife temperature during cutting: -80 °C and -50 °C; nominal thickness of the sections: 60 nm). The ultrathin sections were collected to the standard copper grid, transferred

to the TEM microscope, and observed by means of the standard bright field imaging at the accelerating voltage of 120 kV.

Tensile mechanical properties were measured using a DMA Q800 dynamic mechanical analyzer (TA Instruments, USA) at RT. The specimens had a width of 6 mm and a thickness of about 300 μm . The gauge length between the clamp jaws was 15 mm.

2.2 Cell culture experiments

SAOS-2 human osteosarcoma cell line was used for *in vitro* testing of the PCL-based nanocomposite films. The films were disinfected with 70 % ethanol for 15 min, washed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), and inserted in a 24-well plate (Techno Plastic Products; Trasadingen, Switzerland). The cells were seeded at the density of 10,000 cells/cm² in McCoy's 5A medium (Sigma Aldrich; Burlington, MA, USA) supplemented with 15 % fetal bovine serum (FBS; Gibco – Thermo Fisher Scientific; Waltham, MA, USA), and cultivated for 1, 3, and 7 days under standard culture conditions (37 °C and a humidified air atmosphere with 5 % of CO₂).

For the microscopy observation, the cells were fixed in a 4 % solution of paraformaldehyde in PBS and fluorescently stained for nuclei and actin filaments using 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI) and phalloidin-tetramethylrhodamine conjugate (Sigma-Aldrich), respectively. The cells were photographed on an inverted Olympus IX71 epifluorescence microscope equipped with a DP80 camera (both Olympus; Tokyo, Japan) using a 10 \times lens (N.A. = 0.3). Three independent experiments were performed to determine the cell number.

The metabolic activity of cells was measured by the MTS test (Promega; Madison, WI, USA) using the protocol provided by the manufacturer. Briefly, to obtain the working solution,

the MTS reagent was mixed into Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium and 10 % FBS cultivation medium 1:6 volume/volume. The cells were cultivated in the working solution for 2 h. The solution was then transferred in triplicates to a 96-well plate (100 μ l per well) and the absorbance was measured at 490 and 700 nm as background using a VersaMax plate reader (Eastport, ME, USA). Three independent experiments were performed to measure the cell mitochondrial metabolic activity and each sample type was used in triplicate and measured three times (technical triplicates).

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Molecular structure from FT-IR

FT-IR spectra of the composite samples exhibited contributions from both PCL and gelatin (**Fig. 1**). The characteristic peaks of gelatin were observed at 1652 and 1544 cm^{-1} corresponding to the amide-I [40] and amide-II [41] bands, respectively. The amide-I band is mainly due to C=O stretching vibrations, while amide II band arises due to N-H stretching vibrations strongly coupled to the C-N stretching vibration of gelatin [42, 43]. The peaks observed at \sim 2945 and \sim 2866 cm^{-1} were attributed to asymmetric and symmetric stretching of methylene groups in PCL, respectively. Further peaks assigned to PCL were observed at 1724 cm^{-1} (C=O stretching of the ester carbonyl group); 1472 and 1366 cm^{-1} (CH_2 bending); 1294 cm^{-1} (backbone C-O and C-C stretching in the crystalline phase); 1242 cm^{-1} (asymmetric COC stretching), 1188 cm^{-1} (C-O stretching); 1173 cm^{-1} (symmetric COC stretching); 1108 cm^{-1} ; 1047 cm^{-1} ; 961 cm^{-1} ; and 732 cm^{-1} (CH_2 rocking) [44-47]. The FT-IR spectra of all three types of composites prepared using gelatin obtained from fish, porcine, and bovine skin showed a similar spectral pattern with no major difference. The amide I and II peaks at 1652 and 1544 cm^{-1} are the main indicators which show a clear variation and these two peaks increase

gradually with the increase in the gelatin concentration indicating the presence of gelatin in the samples.

3.2 Nanoscale morphology and crystal structure from SWAXS

PCL is a semicrystalline polymer containing lamellar-stack structures with alternating crystalline and amorphous lamellae [2,3]. All the reflections in the WAXS profiles of the selected samples (**Fig. 2**) were assigned to the orthorhombic crystal lattice of PCL [4]. The profile of the initial PCL powder sample is shown for comparison.

Fig. 2 WAXS profiles of selected samples

The diffraction pattern intensities were normalized to the intensity of (110) reflection. It can be observed that the ratios of particular reflections differ from sample to sample, which is presumably caused by the varying extent of preferential orientation of the PCL crystallites with respect to the direction perpendicular to the film surface, which was caused by the solution casting process, as already observed for PCL-containing solution-cast films in our previous work [5]. The extent of preferential orientation can be assessed based on the comparison of ratios of particular reflections, e.g. (110) to (200), in the respective WAXS profile with the corresponding ratio in the profile of PCL powder sample, in which the orientation of PCL crystallites is fully random (isotropic). Based on this comparison, it can be concluded that in

the pure PCL film, there is some preferential orientation, whereas in the PCL/Gel samples, (PCL/B3, PCL/F3, PCL/P3) the orientation appears to be almost random. This may be due to the addition of a softer gelatin component which presumably reduced the mechanical stress during the crystallization of PCL in the course of the solution casting process. On the other hand, **Fig. 2** shows that the presence of MXene increased the extent of preferential orientation of PCL crystallites. It may have been caused by the steric effects of MXene nanosheets.

The SAXS profiles of all the samples showed the typical PCL profile corresponding to the lamellar stack systems in PCL (**Fig. 3**). The samples with admixtures, i.e., with different types of gelatin and the MXene particles) show little difference with respect to the pure PCL sample except for the small-angle upturn in the low- q region of the SAXS profiles. The small-angle upturn indicates the presence of larger particles or inhomogeneities with sizes at least 25 nm. The real size of these objects cannot be determined due to the low- q limit ($q_{\min} \sim 0.18 \text{ nm}^{-1}$) of the used instrument's q -range. **Fig. 4** shows the SAXS profiles of the PCL/MX/B1 film sample (as an example) and the PCL film sample and the difference profile (PCL/MX/B1 minus the PCL) showing the profile corresponding to the mentioned larger objects alone. The profile of the larger objects corresponds quite well to Porod's law ($I \sim q^{-4}$) plotted in the graph (the line with a slope of -4 in the shown double logarithmic plot). This fact indicates that the small-angle upturn corresponds to the surface scattering (i.e., high- q part of the scattering) of some larger particles having their SAXS knee out of the range of the instrument (it would be found at $q < q_{\min}$). A comparison of the profiles of all the selected samples in **Fig. 3** shows that the small-angle upturn is independent of the presence or absence of MXene. Thus, this small-angle upturn cannot be assigned to the MXene. It is expected that MXene also contributes to the small-angle upturn due to dimensions of MXene particles in the range of tens of nanometers, however, as our comparison shows, their contribution to small-angle scattering is minor with respect to the present polymeric particles. This can be partly explained by the low weight

percentage of MXenes in the sample (0.5 wt%) but mainly by the fact shown by SEM and TEM (Section 3.4) that a substantial part of MXenes was present in the form of large agglomerates.

Fig. 3 SAXS profiles of selected film samples

Fig. 4 SAXS profiles of PCL/MX/B1 film, pure PCL film, and the difference profile

The long period of the PCL lamellar stacks was determined from the position of the first maximum of the 1D correlation function, $\Gamma_1(z)$, of the lamellar structures [6] shown in **Fig. 5**, using the procedure described in [5], which resulted to 12.8 nm. Besides, the PCL long period was also determined from the first maximum of the Lorentz-corrected SAXS profile as described in [5], which provided a value of 13.9 nm.

Fig. 5 1D correlation function of PCL lamellar stacks calculated from SAXS profile of pure PCL film sample

3.3 Mechanical Properties

The mechanical properties of the films were evaluated using tensile tests and the stress-strain curves of pure PCL, PCL/Gel and PCL/MX/Gel composite samples for porcine and bovine gelatin are presented in **Fig. 6**. Basically, the mechanical properties of films depend on many parameters such as the nature of reactants, type of dopants, their compositions and the possible interactions among them. Sometimes the interactions may contribute to the enhancement of mechanical properties or may follow a reverse trend and lead to a decline in their properties. Hence, it is difficult to predict the exact properties of the material, particularly, if a natural polymer such as gelatin (obtained from fish, porcine, and bovine skin) is involved in designing

the matrix. From the tensile experiments, it is evident that the presence of gelatin leads to a slight decrease in the ultimate tensile strength and to an increase in the elongation at break (from ~40 up to ~55 %).

Fig. 6 Tensile stress-stain curves of (a) PCL/P1-3 and PCL/MX/P1-3 and (b) PCL/B1-3 and PCL/MX/B1-3 samples.

The ultimate strength of pure PCL film was 12 MPa and for the shown PCL/Gel composite samples (**Fig. 6**) it was in the range from ~6 to ~10 MPa. Both the decrease in the ultimate strength of PCL/Gel samples and the increase in elongation at break with respect to pure PCL can be expected as the gelatin component is soft and amorphous as opposed to PCL.

The composite samples containing MXene showed a very interesting tensile behavior. The incorporation of MXene nanosheets altered the tensile properties of these hydrogels. Even the small content of MXene (0.5 wt% in all the samples) caused a substantial increase in elongation at break (124–135 % for PCL/MX/P1-3 samples, 96–140 % for PCL/MX/B1-3 samples and 80–120% for PCL/MX/F1-3 samples) and at the same time a clear decrease in the ultimate strength (down to ~6 MPa). The lowest elongation at break for the samples with fish gelatin could be explained by the morphology with the highest roughness, as shown by SEM/SE analyses of the fracture surfaces (Section 3.4). MXene-containing samples thus also showed the highest toughness, which is equal to the integral area under the stress-strain curve. The maximum toughness was observed for the PCL/MX/B2 sample (10.7 J/cm^3) which was almost

three times higher than that of the pure PCL film (4.0 J/cm^3).

This mechanical behavior could be related to the change in crystallinity caused by the presence of MXene particles, as shown by WAXS (see Section 3.2). Besides, the surface of MXene nanosheets has plenty of functional groups that can easily form hydrogen bonding with $-\text{NH}_2$, $-\text{OH}$, and $-\text{COOH}$ groups on gelatin, which may also have contributed to the increased toughness of these materials. In a recent study, conducting MXene-based organohydrogel displayed a similar improvement in the mechanical properties when MXene was incorporated into the hydrogel [48]. The enhancement was primarily attributed to the interactions among different functional groups forming multiple hydrogen bonds in the gel network. In our case, the decrease in tensile strength is another feature, which could be due to the limited concentration of MXene. In our preliminary experiments, the higher concentration of MXene (>0.5) led to the formation of rigid hydrogels that were not stable to form films, so we reduced the concentration of MXene to 0.5%.

3.4 Morphology from SEM and TEM analyses

Morphology of the PCL/MX/Gel samples, which exhibited improved tensile strength (as explained in Section 3.3), was characterized by SEM microscopy (**Fig. 7**), SEM/EDX microanalysis (**Fig. 8**) and TEM analysis (**Fig. 9**).

Figure 7 shows the typical SEM/SE micrographs of cross-sectional fracture surfaces (the SE abbreviation indicates that the micrographs were obtained with a secondary electron detector). The SEM/SE micrographs display mostly topographic contrast [39, 49]. Consequently, the SEM/SE images of polymer blends reveal the phase morphology of the system. In our case we observed quite rough morphology of gelatin particles (smooth rounded objects) in the PCL matrix (background with sharp fracture lines). As documented in **Fig. 7**, the roughness of the structure decreased in the order: PCL/MX/fish gelatin > PCL/MX/bovine gelatin >

PCL/MX/porcine gelatin. It is worth noting that SEM/SE imaging was employed also in fast verification of the morphology of PCL/Gel samples (i.e., the samples without MX); the observed morphologies were similar to those displayed in **Fig. 7**.

Fig. 7: SEM/SE micrographs showing fracture surfaces of all PCL/MX/Gel samples: (a-c) PCL/MC/bovine gelatin, (d-f) PCL/MX/fish gelatin, and (g-i) PCL/MX/porcine gelatin. The columns show, from left to right, the samples with the lowest, intermediate and the highest concentrations of gelatin.

Moreover, the SEM results suggested that at least some MXene nanoparticles form agglomerates in micrometer scale, which were observable as bright white spots in SEM/SE micrographs, whose concentration seemed to increase towards the bottom surface of the

samples. This was further investigated and confirmed by SEM/EDX microanalysis and TEM/BF imaging, as discussed below.

Figure 8 displays typical SEM/EDX spectra of a PCL/MX/Gel sample, which were obtained from the top surface (**Fig. 8a**) and bottom surface (**Fig. 8b**). These spectra were similar for all types on gelatin. The MXene nanoparticles (Ti_2C), which were added to the PCL/MX/Gel composites in this work at concentration 0.5 wt.%, should exhibit additional weak titanium peaks in EDX spectra. The expected low intensity of the titanium peaks is related to the very low concentration of Ti in the prepared composites. The titanium peaks ($\text{TiK}\alpha$ at ~ 0.4 keV and $\text{TiL}\alpha$ at ~ 4.5 keV) were observed only on the bottom surfaces of the samples (compare **Fig. 8a** with **8b**). This indicated that substantial part of MXene nanofiller formed agglomerates that tended to sediment at the bottom of the samples.

Fig. 8: Typical SEM/EDX spectra from the top (a) and bottom (b) part of a PCL/MX/Gel samples. The insets show specific energy regions, in which the weak titanium peaks should be observed. The Pt peaks originate from the Pt coating of the samples for SEM observations.

Figure 9 is a collection of typical TEM/BF micrographs (BF stands for the classical bright field imaging) of the investigated PCL/MX/Gel composites. Part of the MXene nanofiller was quite well dispersed in the polymer matrix (**Fig. 9a**), but substantial portion of the filler

particles formed nanometer scale (**Fig. 9b**) or even micrometer scale agglomerates (**Fig. 9c**). The larger agglomerates tended to sediment during the sample preparation, as confirmed by SEM/EDX results (see **Fig. 8** and the discussion in the previous paragraph).

Fig. 9: Typical TEM/BF micrographs of PCL/MX/Gel composites showing (a) well-dispersed MXene nanosheets, (b) small MXene agglomerates, and (c) very large, microscale MXene agglomerates.

3.5 Cell-material interaction

The cell culture experiments proved that the colonization of the composite materials with SAOS-2 cells is influenced by the presence of MXene in the material, and also by the type and concentration of gelatin in the composite. The fluorescence staining and microscopy of the SAOS-2 cells (**Fig. 10**) show that the confluent layer of cells can be observed after 7 days of cultivation on all samples containing MXene and porcine gelatin at all concentrations. In contrast, the cells on samples containing MXene and bovine or fish gelatin were subconfluent and less homogeneously distributed, and the number of cells decreased with increasing gelatin concentration. This may be due to a higher microscale surface roughness of the samples containing bovine or fish gelatin compared to those containing porcine gelatin. It is known from bone tissue engineering that materials with microscale surface roughness can retard cell

growth, although they can promote osteogenic cell differentiation[50]. Another explanation may be that samples with higher gelatine content provided less mechanical support to the growing cells. Similar results to those obtained for samples with MXene and bovine or fish gelatin were obtained for samples with porcine gelatine not reinforced with MXene, where the least confluent layer of cells is formed on the samples with the highest gelatin concentration. Taken together, we can observe the negative effect of higher gelatin concentration in the composite and the improving effect of MXene in the samples with porcine gelatin but not in the samples with bovine or fish gelatin, probably due to their weaker mechanical properties.

Fig 10: Fluorescence staining of SAOS-2 cells after 7 days of cultivation – blue are cell nuclei stained by DAPI, and red are actin filaments. MX are samples containing 0.5 wt. % of MXene, B – samples containing bovine gelatin, F – samples containing fish gelatin, P – samples containing porcine gelatin, PCL – control poly-ε-caprolactone samples without gelatin and MXene. PS – control tissue culture polystyrene. The representative images for this figure were selected from 15 images of the same sample type.

The measurement of the metabolic activity (**Fig. 11**) of the SAOS-2 cells cultivated on the studied composites confirmed the microscopic observations. Although the results are not statistically significant, we can observe a decrease in the metabolic activity of the SAOS-2 cells in higher concentrations of all types of gelatin on the 7th day of cultivation. We can also observe higher metabolic activity of SAOS-2 cells on samples with porcine gelatin compared to bovine and fish gelatin. On the other hand, we can also see that on the first day of cultivation, the metabolic activity of SAOS-2 cells is higher in the samples with bovine and fish gelatin. This suggests that cell adhesion is easier or faster on these two types of gelatin than on the porcine gelatin, which in turn provides a more suitable environment for cell proliferation. We can also observe a slight increase in the metabolic activity of the SAOS-2 cells in the samples with the intermediate concentration (15 wt. %) of fish or porcine gelatin compared to the samples with the lowest concentration of gelatin. This can be observed in the microscopic images, especially in the samples with porcine gelatin and without MXene.

Fig. 11: Metabolic activity of the SAOS-2 cells cultivated on the studied composites and control pure PCL (PCL) and tissue culture polystyrene (PS) for 1, 3, and 7 days.

3. Conclusions

In this study, we prepared a series of composite films based on PCL, MXene and gelatin that were characterized structurally, morphologically, mechanically and biologically for potential biomedical applications. The performed analyses showed that biological properties were influenced both the type of gelatin and the presence of MXenes. The best biological performance was shown by samples containing the porcine gelatin at a concentration of 15 wt. %. Surprisingly, a higher concentration of gelatin in the construct hindered the cell proliferation on the composite for all types of gelatin. The presence of MXene had a positive effect on the cell confluence on the construct surface. The incorporation of MXene also promoted the tensile properties of the films, which is an important criterion for tissue engineering applications. The ultimate strength of all samples was in the approximate range of 6 to 10 MPa. The morphology of PCL/MX/Gel samples was very rough with particle sizes in the order of magnitude from units to tens of a μm . The surface roughness decreased in the following order: PCL/MX/fish gelatin > PCL/MX/bovine gelatin > PCL/MX/porcine gelatin. The investigated films, in particular the PCL/MX/P1-3 samples, have shown great potential for biomedical applications due to the combination of very good biological and mechanical properties. For example, they can be used as scaffolds for hard and soft tissue engineering and as coatings for biomaterials in order to modulate their interaction with cells. However, there is still much room for improvement of the materials based on these components. It would be desirable to investigate a different type of MXene that does not contain such large agglomerates as the one currently used and could therefore be better dispersed in the polymer matrix. At the same time, it would be useful to repeat similar research using polymer matrices of analogous compositions prepared by a method other than solution casting, which would also allow the

polymer components themselves to intermix better, so that even the particle size of the polymer components is smaller.

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